

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES OF PEDAGOGICAL HIGHER EDUCATION PERSONNEL

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Abstract. *The article deals with issues related to the innovative activities of teachers of higher educational institutions; difficulties and barriers arising in the process of professional activity of teaching staff. In the presented article, the author highlights one of the most difficult issues of teacher professional development in the modern education system. The article discusses the factors that are specific stressors in pedagogical activity and lead to maladjustment and emotional burnout of the teacher. At the same time, the author not only points out the problem areas in the profession of a modern teacher, but also suggests ways to solve these problems by including the teacher in various types of innovative activities and creating a set of measures aimed at developing the personal growth of the teacher, allowing to solve the problem of improving the psychological culture in educational space.*

Keywords: *pedagogical innovation, professional burnout syndrome, professional deformation, resistance to innovation, professional development.*

Introduction. Higher educational institutions, which are centers for the creation of innovative educational concepts, are in the process of searching for optimal methods for developing and shaping the creative qualities of an individual. The growing interest and need for the use of innovative technologies in the educational process in society leads to a global transformation of the role and tasks of teachers. This situation, on the one hand, ensures the high quality of education of professional culture in students, and on the other hand, allows the formation of professional qualities that lead to self-awareness and development as a new innovative type of person. At the current stage of development of higher education, a pedagogue appears as a coach providing an individual educational route, a leader with the ability to promote innovative and creative ideas, an innovator who adapts and promotes new educational projects, and creates new innovative technologies and educational platforms.

In order to implement the state policy "Implementation of modern innovative models of retraining of scientific-pedagogical personnel", the following conditions must be met by the teacher of higher education: correct assessment of the importance of innovations; activation of creative abilities, undisclosed and hidden resources, opportunities; acceptance of goals aimed at self-development in professional activity as a strategic factor of vital activity. The implementation of this task is determined in most cases by the readiness of teachers to activate their internal personal resources, to improve their professional activities with the need and opportunities to search for non-traditional solutions to emerging problems, to creatively implement an innovative approach to education. One of such resources is the individual's innovative potential, which is considered as the ability to correctly set goals, which allows to eliminate the contradiction between the internal capabilities of a person and real productive innovative activity.

Literature analysis and methodology. In developed foreign countries, the issue of achieving an innovative nature of pedagogical activity has been seriously studied since the 60s of the last century. In particular, in the work carried out by researchers such as H. Barnett, J. Bassett, D. Hamilton, N. Gross, R. Carlson, M. Miles, A. Havelock, D. Chen, R. Edem, F. N. Gonobolin, S. M. Godnin, V. I. Zagvyazinsky, V. A. Kan-Kalik, N.V. Kuzmina and V.A. Slastenin, issues such as innovative activity, innovative approach to pedagogical activity, substantiation of innovative ideas and their effective implementation in practice were studied. Innovative activity as an important component of pedagogical culture was studied by N. Azizkhojayeva, Y.V. Bondarevskaya, N.A. Banko, S.D. Mukanova, N.I. Naumkin, M. Ochilov, M. Tojiyev, B. Ziyomukhamedov, N. Sayidahmedov. The work of R.J. Ishmuhamedov, A.A. Abdugadirov, R.A. Mavlonova on innovative processes in the field of education, the work of U.S. Begimkulov, Y.V. Kipriyanova on the issue of creating an innovative environment in educational institutions, the work of A.M. Khan on overcoming psychological obstacles to the introduction of innovations into the educational process, the works of O.R. Badaguyeva, G.T. Musabekova, M. Jumanyozova on the preparation of a young teacher for innovative activities, the works of V.P. Delia on the formation of an innovative educational environment in a humanistic higher education institution became the basis for determining the innovative pedagogical activity of the teacher, its content, and tools.

Results. In the process of research aimed at studying the influence of individual personal qualities on the productivity of innovative activities of innovative pedagogues, it was determined that subjective factors have an impact both at the stage of applying innovations and at the stage of popularization. In this process, the innovative pedagogue acts both as an author of certain innovations and as a creator. This indicates that the effectiveness of pedagogical innovative activities depends on the level of development of the teacher's personal internal potential, intellectual, emotional and creative abilities. Therefore, a high level of self-development of the pedagogue is required for the implementation of innovative activities. This confirms the need to include a program for the development of the personal and creative potential of teachers in the system of psychological support of pedagogical innovative activities. The purpose of this program is to help pedagogues to overcome obstacles in the application of innovations in the educational process. A.F. Balakirev's opinion is noteworthy in terms of revealing the psychological nature of problems in pedagogical innovation activity. In his opinion, the pedagogue realizes that there is a contradiction between the need to achieve innovative goals and the limitations of the created opportunities [1, pp. 97-120]. So, what are the obstacles that teachers face in their innovative activities? In this regard, the problems highlighted by I.Y. Piskareva deserve attention [2, pp. 16-27]:

- Pedagogical (professional): lack of striving for high results of one's work, creativity, interest in using new ideas, pedagogical technologies;
- Psychological: lack of self-improvement, lack of interest in pedagogical innovation;
- Social: dissatisfaction with wages, working conditions, limitations of opportunities for professional growth.

It seems that most of the above psychological obstacles relate to the personal-emotional sphere of teachers, and it is necessary to mention the "professional burnout syndrome" that arises as a result of them.

Discussion. In the conditions of changes taking place in society, high demands are placed not only on the professional knowledge, skills, and abilities of a modern teacher, but also on his personal development and psychological state. According to experts, pedagogical activity is one of the types of professional activity that deforms the human personality the most. [3, pp. 61]. Dissatisfaction with the amount and conditions of labor rights, economic and social-psychological problems related to the decrease in the prestige of the pedagogical profession in society, such as the failure of educational institutions to meet modern requirements, lead to extraordinary psycho-emotional stress in the teacher's work. The scientific results of many foreign researchers also confirm the opinion that the teaching profession is highly stressful. Also, with an increase in work experience, indicators of the psychological and physical health of teachers decrease, a kind of psychological deformation is observed, called the "professional burnout syndrome". The term "professional burnout syndrome" was proposed in 1974 by the American psychologist H.J. Freudenberger. Professional burnout syndrome is a specific psychological state of a person, manifested by emotional and physical exhaustion, alienation from people, as well as the loss of professional plans and hopes, which develops in a person in the course of his professional activity. In the specialized literature, several different definitions of this psychological phenomenon are given [4, pp. 6-13]. This is especially evident in those involved in teaching activities. These negative changes in the nature of the teacher interfere with his professional activities, make communication difficult [5, pp. 83-86]. Today, among the teaching staff, there are cases of boredom and cooling from the profession, which attracted the attention of many representatives of the social sciences. However, the search for effective measures to prevent the occurrence of professional burnout syndrome among teachers is an important task of modern psychological and pedagogical theory and practice.

Today, the modern education system is characterized by the active use of innovative technologies in the pedagogical process. In this process, the psychological readiness of pedagogues to accept systematic updates is one of the most important conditions. The results of a statistical survey conducted in order to determine the attitude of teaching staff of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute to self-professional development are reflected in the following table (Table 1). The participants of this survey expressed their attitudes based on the following criterion: they expressed the degree of relevance of the statements presented in the table to them in the form of points (5 - this statement completely agrees with your opinion; 4 - almost agree; 3 - yes, and no; 2 - no rather than yes; 1 - does not match).

Table 1

The attitude of teaching staff towards their own professional development

№	points (%)					Signs of teacher's attitude to professional development
	1	2	3	4	5	
1	0,0	0,0	18,2	54,5	27,3	I'm trying to learn myself
2	0,0	0,0	31,8	54,5	13,6	No matter how busy I am, I find time to develop
3	13,6	4,5	31,8	36,4	13,6	The obstacles that appear stimulate my activity
4	9,1	4,5	22,7	45,5	18,2	I look for feedback because it helps me to learn and evaluate myself
5	0,0	0,0	18,2	54,5	27,3	I think about my work, I devote a special time to it
6	0,0	9,1	4,5	59,1	27,3	I analyze my feelings and experiences
7	0,0	0,0	40,9	50,0	9,1	I read a lot

8	0,0	9,1	0,0	72,7	18,2	I discuss in detail the issues that interest me.
9	0,0	4,5	13,6	54,5	27,3	I believe in my abilities
10	0,0	0,0	18,2	40,9	40,9	I try to be a more open person
11	0,0	0,0	9,1	81,8	9,1	I know how people around me influence me
12	0,0	0,0	9,1	63,6	27,3	I manage my professional development and achieve positive results
13	0,0	13,6	4,5	27,3	54,5	I like learning new things
14	0,0	0,0	13,6	68,2	18,2	The increase in responsibility does not scare me

Summarizing the numbers presented in the table, we got the following conclusions: self-learner, trying to engage in active communication with others, pedagogues who are confident in their own abilities, supportive of innovations, and are not afraid of increasing responsibility made up 82-85 percent. Those who always devote time to work on themselves, read a lot, analyze their professional experiences are 60-68 percent. Teachers who manage their professional development and communicate freely with people made up 91 percent. At the same time, 50 percent of teachers said that obstacles arising in the work process have a negative impact on their professional activities, 9 percent of teachers said that they do not feel the influence of the surrounding environment, and 36 percent of teachers said that they do not seek feedback. We must admit that this is a large proportion. Also, the presence of employees who are indifferent to the increase in responsibility and news, who do not work on themselves sufficiently, who do not believe in their abilities and positive results, although it is a small percentage, confirms the urgency of the problems in this regard. On the other hand, the innovative activity that activates the creative potential of the pedagogue can serve as an important factor preventing the emergence of the syndrome of professional burnout. In our opinion, the way to eliminate this imbalance is to develop preventive measures that solve the problem of psychological support of pedagogical staff in innovative activities and prevent emotional exhaustion.

Conclusion. It is advisable to create special methodological, psychological and pedagogical programs aimed at motivating the desire of teachers for self-development, personal and professional growth, activating their creative potential in innovative activities in order to eliminate the problems that arise in the innovative activities of teachers. The following scientific and methodological tasks can be recognized as factors that ensure the success of the innovative activity of a university teacher [6]:

- to determine the specifics of the innovative activity of university teachers;
- description of the nature, composition and tasks of the psychological and pedagogical support of the teaching staff of higher educational institutions;
- development and substantiation of a model of psychological and pedagogical support of innovative activities of teachers of higher educational institutions;
- development and substantiation of innovative activities of higher educational institutions and the main directions of psychological and pedagogical support for teachers;
- development and implementation of a set of tools (forms, methods, techniques) that ensure successful innovative activities of the teaching staff of higher education institutions.

The problem of developing the innovative potential of the teaching staff of higher education is complex and multifaceted, closely related to social, political and economic changes in the life of society. The fulfillment of the above tasks serves to educate a modern teacher who is

ready for self-development in a rapidly changing educational system, who sets his professional duty and professional activity as an important priority, ready for constant retraining and updating.

REFERENCES

1. Balakirev A.F. Zatrudneniya uchitelej v innovacionnoj deyatel'nosti. [Difficulties of teachers in innovative activities]. Dissertation of the candidate of pedagogical sciences. Shuya, 2000.
2. Piskareva I.E. Formirovanie gotovnosti budushchih uchitelej k innovacionnoj deyatel'nosti [Forming the readiness of future teachers for innovative activities]. Dissertation of the candidate of pedagogical sciences. Kostroma, 2000.
3. Gnezdilova O.N. Psihologicheskie aspekty innovacionnoj deyatel'nosti pedagoga [Psychological aspects of innovative activity of a teacher]. Psychological Science and Education, 2006, No 4, pp. 61-65.
4. Chikaryova E.A. Sindrom professional'nogo (emocional'nogo) vygoraniya v pedagogicheskoj srede [The syndrome of professional (emotional) burnout in the teaching environment]. Printing house Khabarovsk Industrial and Economic College, 2018, 31 p.
5. Nerush G. Professional'noe vygoranie kak forma professional'nyh destrukcij [Professional burnout as a form of professional destruction]. News of Saratov University, 2012, No 12, pp 83-87.